

BASIC LINGUISTIC MEANS AND STRATEGIES FOR CREATING HUMOROUS AND SATIRICAL EFFECTS IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE

Mahmadaminov Mirqosim

Karshi irrigation va agrotechnological institute English teacher

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Abstract: This article explores the main stylistic devices of creating humorous effect in politicians' speech. The main types of stylistic devices are explained and examples are provided. The role of literary devices is crucial in creating satire or humor therefore this paper gives some examples of famous politicians who used some linguistic means to create humorous effect in political speeches.

Key words: irony, paradox, antithesis, parody, euphemism, hyperbole, sarcasm, allusion, political irony.

The modern world's political discourse is undergoing a number of changes. It is losing its formal tone and taking on the characteristics of a talk show with a high level of entertainment. The audience is no longer willing to accept bare information, but it is content with infotainment [Fialkova, Yelenevskaya, 201]. At the same time political discourse pursues its main aim – gaining and withholding power [Van Dijk, 2009]. Modern politicians use a variety of strategies to win over supporters, the most common of which are persuasion and manipulation. Humour and satire are increasingly popular ways to increase impact. They assist in conveying additional meaning, ambiguity, and contribute to the speaker's image. Many researchers studied stylistic devices, humour, humorous and satirical effect, and the role of stylistic devices in eliciting laughter. Every scientist had a different perspective on the role of stylistic devices in provoking laughter. The research into the use of language to produce humorous effects in general is diverse and extensive. N. Norrik, for example, looked at stylistic devices in the context of their dominant function in establishing comedic effect [Norrik, 1993, 124]. Allogisms [Chiaro, 1992, 58]; oxymoron [Hughes, 1983, 47]; word play and ambiguity that is resolved in context and communicative situation [Nash, 1985, 241]; polysemy and homonymy as means of creating humorous effect [Arnold, 1976, 103]; pun [Vinogradov, 1981, 137]; occasionalisms based on contextual interplay of word mean [Vinogradov (Galperin, 1991, 86)].

The tendency to use humour and satire in politics as a means of influencing the reader's and audience's point of view was recently observed and analysed from various points of view. Here are some of the examples of studies done to investigate language means and linguistic devices of satire and humour: the impact of exposure to political parody as a means of achieving political efficacy [Becker, 2014, 424–425]; the effects of political humour on message persuasiveness, analysed in context of the extant political entertainment theory [LaMarre, 2014, 401]; the affect effect of sarcastic political humour through negative emotions [Lee, 2014, 307–308]; journalistic humorous commentary on Twitter challenging norms of objectivity and independence [Molyneux, 2015, 1–2] and blurring the lines between news and entertainment [Mourão, 2015, 1–2]; the influence of parody humour as a way of establishing sympathy and enjoyment in shaping credibility and trust of political figures (Peifer, 2016, 173); the use of conceptual metaphors in newspapers to create humour as a means of downgrading others or gaining the readers' sympathy through laughter [Perez-Hernandez, 2016, 541–542].

Stylistics is a branch of linguistics that plays an important role in the creation of humour and satire. Because they created a lot of humorous and satirical effect and are used in more

humorous texts and political speeches, stylistic devices of expressiveness should be investigated more thoroughly. During my research work, the use of irony, metaphor, metonymy, personification, oxymoron, antithesis, pun, hyperbole, sarcasm was confirmed. Metaphor, metonymy, hyperbole, pun, irony, personification, and oxymoron are used more frequently in humorous texts and in literature as well as in political field than others. Depending on the listener's or reader's background, satire and humour can have a positive or negative impact. If the speaker can control his satirical and humorous words, he can have a significant impact on his audience. In most cases, however, satire is difficult to comprehend unless the audience has a thorough understanding of satirical techniques. These devices are more common and interesting in humour, pragmatics, and humorous situations. The following stylistic devices of expressiveness are used to create humorous and satirical effect:

Irony. Irony is a stylistic device in which contradictory statements or situations reveal a reality that is different from what appears to be true. The effectiveness of irony as a literary device depends on the reader's expectations and understanding of the disparity between what "should" happen and what "actually" happens in a literary work. This can be in the form of an unforeseen outcome of an event, a character's unanticipated behaviour, or something incongruous that is said.

Political irony is a sense of oppositeness or contrast in speech or writing that is related to politics. In general, political irony falls into the word is used to describe an outcome that is contradictory to what is expected. Most often, this form of irony seeks to point out contradictions in politics in a wry or amusing way.

Modern speakers and writers use the phrase "political irony" in a variety of ways. Many of these involve satirical or witty analysis of current politics. Political irony is usually related to humour; many expressions of politically ironic speech or writing are intended to entertain through pointing out contradictions in the political field. Despite the entertainment value, there are many instances where a real criticism of politics is couched in ironic comedy.

One type of political irony is the criticism of political candidates for reversals on issues, or actions that go counter to what they have expressed in the past. Other expressions of politically ironic speech evaluate the overall political feelings of the current time. Satirical commentators may use political irony to criticize the way parts of an electorate respond to certain issues. These kinds of writers may also use the same ideas in criticizing a presidential administration, a parliament, or other form of leadership.

The term "political irony" is widely used in the media. It's been the name of a category in various web periodicals, as well as the title of blogs and social media pages. It usually represents a joking take on current events or political issues. This rhetorical strategy is also used by some pundits when writing syndicated columns for magazines or newspapers. This type of irony is frequently seen in political cartoons, in addition to being a common use of rhetoric in text. It can be sarcastic or humorous at times, or it can be quite hostile at others.

Irony in political speeches can come across as bitter, especially when it is directed at opponents. In the following example, Donald Trump uses ambiguous irony when speaking about Hillary Clinton:

"I am sure Hillary is going to laugh quite a bit tonight, sometimes even at appropriate moments" [Al Smith Dinner 20.10/2016].

This remark conveys an implicit meaning, referring to a popular opinion that Hillary is devoid of sense of humour, and all her emotions, including smile and laughter are planned before by her image makers.

Showman and commentator Jay Leno makes a premature conclusion about Mrs Clinton's presidency:

"Yesterday all five living presidents gathered for the opening of the George W. Bush presidential library in Dallas. Well, six living presidents if you count Hillary in 2016."

[<http://politicalhumor.about.com/od/2016-Election/fl/2016-Election+Jokes.htm>]

It is done on purpose to create a humorous effect. The speaker hints at the fact that the result of the elections is already known, despite the continuing president race. Ironically enough, what was obvious for many, did not come true.

The following is an example of veiled mockery aimed at one of the candidates in the pre-election campaign:

"Jeb Bush's brother Neil said that their mother has "come around" to the idea of Jeb running for president in 2016. Because if there's anything that says you're qualified to be president, it's your own mom saying, I guess you could do it." [<http://politicalhumor.about.com/>].

The irony here is based on a childish belief that mother is always right and the gravity of the event, which is not intended for children. Bringing these ideas together creates an ironic paradox with an obvious absurd conclusion for the audience.

Humour and irony often play a positive role and contribute to a person's image. Ivanka Trump, daughter of Donald Trump (a candidate for presidency then) characterizes her father, using wordplay:

"When it comes "to building bridges" he can do so figuratively but also has the rare ability to do so literally on time and under budget"

[YouTube. Donald Trump Presidential Announcement Full Speech, 16.06.15].

In this sentence, the speaker uses the collocation "to build bridges" in both a literal and figurative sense. This contrast has a comedic effect, relaxes the audience, and keeps their attention.

Paradox. A paradox is also considered to be one of the techniques used to create a satiric effect. As [Al-Ebadi, H, et al., 2020, p.1448] points out, texts require professional attention in order to stand out in addition to conveying their communicative message. A paradox, according to Abrams and Harpham [2015, p. 267], is a statement that appears to be logically opposing or silly on the surface but is interpretable in a way that makes sense. A paradox is a self-contradictory statement that tries to convey a message by presenting two completely different things.

In the apparent sense, a paradox has an idea that is not acceptable or logical, and it is based on linguistic contradiction. One of the characteristics of good satire is that it attacks topics, and presenting paradoxical things achieves this.

For example:

War is peace.

Freedom is slavery.

My weakness is my strength.

In these three examples the speaker says something but here the listener is going to understand the intended meaning behind the ideas meant. So war is obsolete not peace but it is something

not peaceful at all. Freedom is the obviously opposite of slavery, and a weakness is not going to reflect any strength. Paradox is considered one of the most interesting linguistic device and an effective tool to get the attention of listeners.

Antithesis. Antithesis is a literary device in which two opposing elements are juxtaposed using a parallel grammatical structure. The word antithesis, which means "to set opposite," comes from Greek and refers to when something or someone is directly opposite or the obverse of something or someone else. Antithesis is defined by Leech [1969, p. 67] as a "literary device in which formal parallelism is combined with an implication of contrast". In contrary to paradox, two similar things are emphasized to be distinctive. This structure is common in satire because it targets audiences who believe that what is presented as dissimilar is similar. Acceptable, correct wisdom or advice is the idea in opposition. Antithesis has two parts to describe characteristics and contrast in meaning in the linguistic context.

For instance:

In Paradise Lost, John Milton says: "Better to reign in Hell than serve in Heaven."

The contrasting ideas of reign and serve and Hell and Heaven are placed in this sentence to achieve an antithetical effect where readers can understand and get the gist of the idea.

"Man proposes, God disposes"

"No pain, no gain."

"Love is an ideal thing, marriage is a real thing." [Goethe].

"That's one small step for man, one giant leap for mankind." [Neil Armstrong]

"To err is human; to forgive divine." [Alexander Pope]

"It was the best of times, it was the worst of times, it was the age of wisdom, it was the age of foolishness, it was the epoch of belief, it was the epoch of incredulity, it was the season of Light, it was the season of Darkness, it was the spring of hope, it was the winter of despair, we had everything before us, we had nothing before us, we were all going direct to Heaven, we were all going direct the other way..." [Charles Dickens].

Hyperbole. Hyperbole, according to Abrams and Harpham [2015, p. 28], is "a type of text that allows and encourages the reader to branch off into other texts at will, making the reading experience nonlinear, open, and variable."

Making an exaggerated comparison is a satirical technique that aims for one of two outcomes: either the two comparative things share the same quality or the comparison aims to exaggerate that quality, especially when a characteristic is negative. Alternatively, they could be completely different, imparting a positive trait to the party that does not have a negative state within it. The literal meaning of hyperbole is not the intended meaning. Hyperbole is a figure of speech which is used when someone wants to exaggerate what they mean or emphasize a point. It comes from the Greek word to mean "excess" and is often used to make something sound much bigger, better, funnier, or more dramatic than it actually is. Hyperbole is a useful tool in language.

For instance:

I'm so hungry, I could eat an elephant.

My dad will kill me when he comes home.

Harper Lee writes in her book "To Kill a Mockingbird":

“A day was twenty-four hours long but seemed longer. There was no hurry, for there was nowhere to go, nothing to buy and no money to buy it with, nothing to see outside the boundaries of May comb County.”

The author is using hyperbole in this example to emphasize how slow and boring the town is. The hyperbolic phrases in this sentence help the reader understand the situation because the sentence would be less emotive without them.

Parody. A parody is a deliberate exaggeration of a particular writer, artist, or genre in order to produce a comic effect. In parody, the humorous effect is achieved by imitating and overstressing noticeable features of a famous piece of literature, similar to how caricatures highlight certain characteristics of a person to achieve a humorous effect. To be successfulness of parody, the addressee must be aware of the original topic (or personality) being mocked. Parody examples are frequently confused with satire examples. Although parody can be used to develop satire, it is distinct from it in some ways. To create a comic effect, parody directly imitates a subject. Satire, on the other hand, mocks a subject without imitating it directly. Furthermore, satire aims to correct societal flaws by criticizing them.

In shows that blend parody and satire, we may see extremely hilarious examples of parody in our daily television viewing. The Daily Show, The Colbert Report, and The Larry Sanders Show, for example, are known for imitating well-known political figures, allowing them to target what they consider to be unintelligent political and social viewpoints.

Gulliver’s Travels by Jonathan Swift is a satire on contemporary England as well as a parody of travel narratives. As England’s empire expanded to new lands, it became a hub for navigation and exploration. Adventure and travel stories about strange lands became increasingly popular. Sarcasm. Sarcasm is an ironic remark with a sense of humour that is intended to mock or satirize something. When someone is being sarcastic, they are saying something that is not what they mean. Sarcasm, as a literary device, can convey a writer’s or character’s true feelings of frustration, anger, and even derision, albeit masked by humour and wording that is inconsistent with the intended meaning. However, because sarcastic statements contradict the speaker’s true meaning and intent, it can be difficult for writers to use this literary device effectively without proper context or tone. The purpose of sarcastic comments is usually to express feelings of frustration, anger, or distaste through stating one idea but meaning another, as well as moderating the statement with humour.

John Green writes in his novel titled “Turtles All the Way Down”, “Yes, well, in that respect and many others, American high schools do rather resemble prisons,” John Green writes in his novel Turtles All the Way Down. The speaker is mocking characteristics of American high schools that resemble prisons in a figurative sense, not literally. Metal detectors, student detention as a form of punishment, mandatory attendance, crowded classrooms, and even poor infrastructure are examples of this. Green’s literary device of sarcasm allows for amusing mockery of figurative parallels between American high schools and prisons.

Following examples are used in everyday speech:

Ugliness can be fixed, stupidity is forever.

Propaganda is amazing. People can be led to believe anything. [Alice Walker]

Stop worrying about growing old. And think about growing up. [Philip Roth]

There are times when parenthood seems nothing more than feeding the hand that bites you. [Peter De Vries].

Euphemism. Euphemism is a figure of speech that is frequently used to replace a word or phrase that is associated with a concept that may cause discomfort to others. Euphemism is figurative language that is used to replace harsh, impolite, or unpleasant language. As a way of softening the impact of what is being said, this literary device allows someone to say what they mean indirectly rather than using literal language. For the sake of politeness, discretion, and other means of communication mitigation, this would be the case. Death, sex, aging, being fired, bodily functions, and other abstractions are all covered by euphemisms.

In everyday conversation and writing, there are numerous examples of euphemism. Here are some examples of how this figure of speech is used:

porcelain throne (toilet) bun in the oven (pregnancy)

senior (old) economically challenged (poor)

between jobs (unemployed) big-boned (overweight)

enhanced interrogation (torture) well-off (rich)

correctional facility (prison) thin on top (bald)

Conclusion. This paper has attempted to determine and analyse different ways and means of creating a satirical and humorous effect in the modern political discourse. Presently, more and more researches are being done to investigate the linguistic tools and stylistic devices of creating satire and humour in political discourse. Studying and analysing the various ways of making humorous effect in political discourse allow us to understand the intention of humour and satire which are being used in politics whether by politicians or against politicians. Furthermore, researches being done on this topic helps to discover new ways of creating jokes and humour in politicians speeches. This, in turn comes handy for political world people to make their speech much more amusing and brighter as well helps them to attract the attention of the audience.

The research results presented above allow us to conclude that the specific patterns of using language means and stylistic devices of humorous and satirical effect in political discourse is depend largely on irony, joke, euphemism, hyperbole, sarcasm, allusion, folks, anecdotes, metaphor, metonymy, cartoon and meme.

Modern politicians use irony and humour quite a lot for different purposes: to attack opponents, to win support, to draw the attention of the audience, to strengthen their own image, to amuse public. The examples, analysed in this research paper, are based on wordplay, ambiguity, absurdity etc. The use of irony and humour makes a speech brighter, more impressive and persuasive. Skilful speakers take advantage of these devices to produce a greater effect on the audience and reach their aims;

-hyperbole, irony, metaphor are the basic stylistic devices in making humorous effect;

-although the stylistic devices used in political discourse are very similar to each other in English and Uzbek language, they have differences in the meaning and the amount of the application.

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